

Table 1. Number of *C. suppressalis* eggs consumed by *M. vittaticollis* for 1 d at a temperature range of 25-30 °C.

Stage	Consumed <i>C. suppressalis</i> eggs (no. d ⁻¹)	
	Mean ± SD ^a	Range
Nymph		
1 st instar	1.7 ± 0.67	1-3
2 nd instar	2.5 ± 0.71	2-4
3 rd instar	13.3 ± 5.58	8-24
4 th instar	184.3 ± 45.2	162-246
Adult		
Male	102.7 ± 23.23	72-147
Female	158.7 ± 53.56	78-246

^a Av of 10 individuals ± SD.

Table 2. Parameter estimates of the functional response equation for *M. vittaticollis* feeding on *C. suppressalis* eggs at a temperature range of 25-30 °C.

Stage	Parameter estimates ^a		Asymptotic SE	
	<i>a</i>	<i>Th</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>Th</i>
4 th -instar nymph	9.9381	0.0037	30.5532	0.0011
Adult male	4.5044	0.0070	4.6008	0.0009
Adult female	4.7314	0.0044	5.3486	0.0009

^a *a* = attack rate, *Th* = handling time.

Th was significantly higher, indicating that they have lower feeding capacities than females.

The figure illustrates the relationship between number of SSB eggs attacked and initial egg density. The number of SB eggs attacked by one fourth-instar larva, an adult male, and an adult female increased with prey density. As initial density increased, the consumption of SSB eggs by the cricket increased at a decreasing rate

until a satiation level was reached. The functional response of fourth-instar larva, adult male, and adult female on SSB eggs fitted the Holling's Type II model. This model has also been found to fit the feeding behavior of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on planthopper eggs and *Pardosa pseudoannulata* on brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers. ■

Functional response of *M. vittaticollis* on SSB eggs.

Bioassay of *Fusarium pallidoseum* (Cooke) Sacc., (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes) against leaf folder

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Greenhouse studies assessed the pathogenicity of *Fusarium pallidoseum* on rice leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenée at 28.5 °C and between 88 and 90% relative humidity. The pathogen was tested at spore concentrations of 0-1 × 10⁷ conidia mL⁻¹. A stock solution of 1 mL was diluted with sterile distilled water, i.e., 100, 1000, etc., which meant 1 part of the fungus suspension was diluted in 99 or 999 parts of water. Thirty third-instar larvae were dipped for 2 to 3 s in each concentration. Treated larvae were transferred to filter paper and incubated in a petri dish containing fresh rice leaves.

Mortality was determined after 1 wk of incubation and the percentage adjusted using Abbott's formula. Probit analysis

showed that 5.49 × 10³ conidia mL⁻¹ was the effective concentration for LD₅₀ of *F. pallidoseum* (see table). ■

Mortality dose of *F. pallidoseum* on rice leaf folder larvae.

Larvae used (no.)	χ^2 ^a	Slope	LD ₅₀ (conidia mL ⁻¹)	Fiducial limit
180	9.456	0.622	5.49 × 10 ³	2.49 – 12.11 × 10 ³

^a P < 0.05. Heterogeneity analysis: variance = 0.0246. Results of χ^2 for the above analysis = 13.86719.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Evolving patterns of rat control at IIRI

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This report discusses the changes made at IIRI that have reduced rat problems. A 1987 survey (by N. S. Ahmed and others) indicated that 86% of some 171 field experiments, including 11 trials that were completely lost, suffered rat damage. The lost data were valued at US\$370,000 and the direct cost of con-

trol US\$402,000 (see figure). In 1989, control costs had risen to US\$473,000 but by 1994, they had dropped to US\$52,000, an annual savings of US\$421,000 and lost data costs were also decreased.

Early rat control at IIRI consisted of galvanized iron fences with a single electrified wire at the top. The system had 24-h surveillance by 160 persons involved in rat control. Starting in 1989, an integrated system of rat control, combining six management practices, has led to the dramatic reductions in